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TYPES OF FUNCTIONAL EQUIPMENT NEEDED FOR BEEKEEPING

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Abstract: *This article examines the technological and structural development of beekeeping systems with particular attention to hive design, materials, equipment, and modern monitoring technologies. The study analyzes the historical evolution of beekeeping from the 17th century to the present, highlighting key innovations such as the introduction of frame hives, modular structures, and automated monitoring systems. Special emphasis is placed on the hive as the main spatial and functional unit of the bee colony, responsible for maintaining optimal thermal conditions, humidity balance, ventilation, and the organization of cellular structures.*

The paper also reviews the principal types of hive systems, including vertical modular systems, horizontal hives, and combined designs, and evaluates the influence of construction materials such as wood, polymers, and composite structures on durability and thermal insulation. In addition, the research considers the technological equipment used in modern beekeeping, including tools for hive maintenance, honey extraction mechanisms, supplementary feeding systems, treatment and prevention devices, and digital monitoring technologies for controlling temperature, humidity, and colony activity.

Particular attention is given to ergonomic design principles for beekeeping tools and the safety systems used to protect beekeepers during prolonged work. The study also discusses transport and storage systems for hives, as well as modern approaches to colony health management and productivity optimization. The findings demonstrate that the integration of biological knowledge, engineering design, and digital technologies significantly improves the efficiency, sustainability, and productivity of modern beekeeping while preserving the natural behavior and health of bee colonies.

Keywords: *Beekeeping, hive systems, design, materials, mechanisms, technological structure.*

Beekeeping was organized and became structural in the 17th–18th centuries, and the main innovations during this period included the improvement of wooden or clay hives with strong, opening boards, which facilitated maintenance and control of the bee colony. In the 18th–19th centuries, the use of hives with removable frames and frame systems was initiated, which made it possible to standardize the cell structure and significantly facilitate the honey collection process, at the same time new methods of monitoring the health of families were introduced, and the comfort of work was significantly improved. In the 20th century, the stage of industrial and multifunctional development of beekeeping was formed, during which the structure of hives was adapted to different seasonal conditions, the materials used became more durable, functional equipment was integrated with feeding, cleaning and ventilation systems, as well as ergonomic and material improvements were made with the use of modular, lightweight and multifunctional solutions. The 21st century is

characterized as an innovative phase, during which intelligent and automated systems are used that control temperature, humidity, and nutrition. Ecological and sustainable materials such as wood, composites, and recyclable plastics are widely used, and the design is shaped by functional and ergonomic principles, while ensuring the preservation of the natural behavior of bees and the comfort of the beekeeper's work (Fig.1).

Fig.1 Stage of development of modern systems

The organization of beekeeping farms is based on an in-depth study of the biological characteristics of insects. Any technological process performed with bees involves a combination of properly designed equipment, structural elements and control mechanisms. Modern scientific approaches combine engineering, biological and ecological principles with the aim of ensuring the viability of the family, the quality of honey and the efficiency of production.

The hive is the main spatial and functional unit of the bee colony as a single vital system. It is an environment where the processes that are vital for the vital activity of the bee colony are ensured: stable maintenance of the thermal regime, balanced regulation of ventilation and humidity, effective formation and development of cellular structures, uninterrupted organization of the natural movement paths of bees, as well as safe and targeted preservation of food reserves.

The full implementation of the above processes is possible only in the case of a scientifically substantiated and properly designed hive, the structure of which takes into account the biological and behavioral characteristics of bees, as well as the requirements of the internal relationships and spatial organization of the bee colony [1].

In practice, different hive systems are used:

1. Dadant–Blatt (fig. 2),
2. Langstroth–Root (fig. 3),
3. Layens (fig. 4),
4. Foam and composite hives (fig. 5).

Fig.2 Dadant–Blatt

Fig.3 Langstroth–Root

Fig.4 Layens

Fig.5 Foam and composite hives

The most common materials are wood, polyurethane, polystyrene. The choice of material affects thermal insulation, durability and ventilation efficiency.

The hive is the main spatial and functional unit of the bee colony as a unified living system.

It is an environment where processes vital to the life of the bee colony are ensured: stable maintenance of the thermal regime, balanced regulation of ventilation and humidity, effective formation and development of cellular structures, uninterrupted organization of the natural movement routes of bees, as well as safe and targeted preservation of food reserves.

Even the smallest beekeeping tool has biological and technical significance, combs reduce the risk of damage to nectar-collecting bees, smoking devices change the collective behavior of the bee colony, reducing aggression, and frame combs reduce mechanical damage.

The new generation of beekeeping tools are designed with comfortable handles, dimensions appropriate to human biomechanics, and a non-slip, heat-resistant handle, and this feature is important for long-term work, lasting 10–12 hours during seasonal periods.

Honey separation is carried out by mechanical sawing (fig.6), centrifugation and vibrating

mechanisms (fig.7), and each method provides different qualitative indicators of honey: water percentage, density, and preservation of terpene compounds.

Fig.6 Mechanical sawing

Fig.7 Centrifugation and vibrating mechanism

Supplemental feeding is important in weak spring periods, and is applied with stem feeders (Fig.8), top-type containers (Fig. 9), and wide dividers (Fig. 10).

Fig.8 Stem feeders

Fig.9 Top-type containers

Fig.10 Wide dividers

Intensive beekeeping uses disinfectant devices (Fig. 11), precise dosing tools (Fig. 12), and vaporizers (Fig.13).

Fig.11 Disinfectant devices

Fig.12 Precise dosing tools

Fig.13 Vaporizers

The hive is a spatial, physiological and ecological unit for the bee colony. It provides the vital conditions for the life of bees:

1. Thermoregulation. The hive maintains the necessary temperature for the honeycomb (34–36 degrees Celsius) through a vertical and horizontal cellular structure, which is important for the development of cells and the activity of worker bees.

2. Humidity balance. The humidity inside the hive is controlled, preventing the formation of mold and preserving the natural quality of honey.

3. Formation of cellular structures. The internal structure of the hive ensures the efficient distribution of honey, royal jelly and brood, while maintaining the honeycomb gaps (6–9 mm) and the natural movement paths of the bees.

4. Transport corridors. The corridors of the hive ensure the free and uninterrupted movement of bees from the cellular part to the food stores, reducing the need for intervention.

5. Food storage. The hive protects the honey and fruit stores from predators and climatic fluctuations, creating a stable microclimate.

When designing a hive, it is necessary to take into account the behavioral characteristics of

bees, including dance communication, search routes and grouping behavior. Therefore, each hive is built based on not only physical, but also biological laws. Below are some of the features necessary for the design of hives [2].

Structural types and types of developmental implications:

1. Vertical modular systems (Fig. 14). Vertical systems contain standard frames that are arranged from top to bottom and provide high modularity. They are suitable for industrial farms, as they facilitate the inspection of the honeycomb and honey. They maintain the honeycomb gaps and ensure a constant temperature in the honeycomb.

2. Horizontal systems (Fig. 15). Horizontal systems are close to the structure of natural cells and require minimal intervention. It contributes to the natural growth of cells and the preservation of bee behavior. More suitable for small farms and organic farms, but requires more experience and skill.

3. All-Russian and variable-volume systems (Fig. 16). These systems combine vertical and horizontal features. Their flexibility allows them to adapt to both production and natural conditions. However, they require a complex design approach and additional material investments.

Fig.14 Vertical modular systems

Fig.15 Horizontal systems

Fig.16 All-Russian and variable-volume systems

Functional zones of the hive and design requirements:

1. Cellular part. Centralized location, ensures stability of temperature and humidity, being the primary cellular structure.

2. Food storage zone. Located in the upper modules, provides easy extraction and maintains the natural behavior of the bee.

3. Ventilation holes. They provide constant ventilation, prevent the formation of condensation points and maintain a healthy microclimate in the honeycomb.

4. Transport corridors. Small honeycomb gaps and the correct arrangement of the corridors allow bees to move freely and without obstruction.

Structural materials and physical requirements:

1. Wood. High thermal insulation, recyclability, requires preventive disinfection and care.

2. Composites and plastics. Has a long service life, minimal care, high resistance to moisture.

3. Foam and insulating materials. Low weight, high insulation and stability to microclimatic fluctuations.

4. Physical requirements include the combined level of thermal insulation, material strength, replaceability of damaged parts and safety in contact with food.

Standard size recommendations:

1. Vertical (Langstroth). Height: 450–500 mm, width: 435–470 mm, honeycomb gap: 6–9 mm, weight: 15–20 kg.

2. Horizontal (Top-bar). Height: 300–350 mm, width: 900–1200 mm, honeycomb gap: 6–9 mm, weight: 10–15 kg.

These dimensions are based on standard models and can be changed depending on the local climate, bee breed and production volume.

In beekeeping, tools have not only technical significance, but also biological, ergonomic and operational significance. Each tool is designed in such a way that the natural behavior of bees is preserved, interference is minimized, and work efficiency is ensured.

Beekeepers (Fig. 15) are designed to gently remove bees without damaging the honeycomb structure. They allow for the integrity of the passages to be maintained, prevent condensation, and reduce the risk of bee injury. The design and dimensions of the beekeepers are designed to follow the natural movement paths of bees, ensuring minimal disruption and high efficiency.

Smokers (Fig. 16) calm the collective behavior of bees and reduce aggression. The smoke causes the bees to become calm, which allows them to open the hives, remove or install frames without the chaos caused by the intervention. Smokers are especially important in large farms, where the mass activity of bees is intense, and any intervention can damage the structure of the cells.

Frame clamps (Fig.17) are designed for removing and installing frames, reducing the likelihood of mechanical damage. With the help of clamps, the integrity of the cellular structure is maintained, the work is performed quickly, efficiently and safely, and the bees receive minimal stress during the intervention.

Sticks, guides and horizontal/vertical clamps (Fig. 18). They are used to open cells, check honey and move frames. Each tool is designed taking into account the behavioral characteristics of bees: dance communication, search routes and compaction behavior.

The new generation of beekeeping tools is designed based on the principles of human physiology and biomechanics to ensure fatigue reduction, injury prevention and precise work during long work.

Comfortable handles. The handles are designed so that the tool can be held for a long time without muscle tension. This reduces the load on the shoulder, hand and neck muscles and allows you to work for long hours while maintaining accuracy.

Dimensions corresponding to human biomechanics. The length, width and weight of the tools are calculated based on the average physiological data of a person. This ensures a natural flow of movements, increases accuracy and reduces the likelihood of muscle and joint injuries.

Non-slip and heat-resistant handle. The material of the tools provides a secure grip, balanced force transmission, and durability in different climatic conditions. This makes it possible to work in both high and low temperatures without loss of control.

Efficiency of large-scale seasonal work. Comfort and safety are important in conditions where the beekeeper works for 10–12 hours in a row, opening hives, monitoring the content of cells, collecting honey, and ensuring the stability of the cellular microclimate [3].

Convenience of cleaning and disinfection. The materials of the tools must be resistant to moisture, temperature fluctuations, and wear in order to maintain high work efficiency and bee health.

Fig.15 Beekeeper

Fig.16 Smokers

Fig.17 Frame clamps

Fig.18 Horizontal /vertical clamps

Technological significance. New tools increase the speed of work, allow for complex operations while maintaining the integrity of the cells, reduce interference, and improve the preservation of honey quality.

Types of honey separation, cleaning, and processing systems.

Mechanical saws (Fig.19).

Structure. Extractors are mainly composed of frame cabinets, rotor or brush extraction systems and honey collection containers. The mechanism ensures natural separation of honey without damaging the cells.

Functional features: Extractors allow for quick, safe separation of honey. The water content, density and valuable terpene compounds of honey are preserved.

Disadvantages: Mechanical extractors operate at medium productivity and require double working stages for very large production volumes.

Classification: Suitable for small and medium-sized farms, where the preservation of naturalness and the minimum need for intervention prevail.

Fig.19 Mechanical saws

Fig.20 Centrifugation systems

Fig.21 Vibrating mechanisms

Structure: Centrifugation mechanisms consist of frame fixing devices, speed-controlled rotation systems and separation containers.

Operational advantages: High productivity, fast complete separation of honey, temperature control, preservation of the honey microclimate. Centrifugation allows working with large volumes without damaging the cells.

Disadvantages: These systems require electricity or manual labor, a large weight of the device and constant attention to maintenance.

Classification: Suitable for industrial and semi-industrial farms, where speed and productivity prevail.

Vibrating mechanisms (Fig. 21).

Structure: Vibrating devices are small, light and portable, designed for natural separation of honey without interference with the cells.

Operational advantages: Ensure safe, natural separation of honey, minimal interference with bee behavior. Suitable for small farms, where the organic method prevails.

Disadvantages: Limited productivity and not suitable for industrial use.

Classification: For organic and small farms, where the preservation of naturalness prevails.

Filtration and aging systems.

Structure: Includes multi-stage filtration networks, settling tanks, mechanisms for removing foam layers.

Operational advantages: Ensure high-quality purification of honey, reduce the risk of fermentation, preserve natural active ingredients and terpene compounds.

Disadvantages: Long and labor-intensive process, requires technical knowledge and supervision, especially during the settling and foam layer removal stages.

Classification: Suitable for all types of farms, especially those where the priority is product quality and long-term storage [4].

The safety of the beekeeper is ensured by a multi-layer system, which includes a masked cap to protect the delicate parts of the face and head, a thick fabric uniform to protect the entire body from punctures, anti-stain gloves to protect the hands, and resistant shoe elements to protect the feet during

work on soil and stone. This system provides physical protection from aggressive attacks by bees, as well as reduces the risk of injuries and allergic reactions [7,8].

The choice of materials and technological structure are of great importance for the safety and working comfort of the beekeeper. The materials should have the following properties:

1. Air circulation - providing moderate cooling of the body in hot climates,
2. Heat-resistant - preventing overheating of the body and damage to the material,
3. Lightweight - reducing fatigue during prolonged work,
4. Anti-sweat - maintaining body moisture and providing comfort.

The above requirements are particularly high in hot climates and in the case of long-term work (10–12 hour shifts).

In the current field of protective clothing, there are a number of technical solutions that differ in terms of structure, breathability, safety level, functionality and service life. A comparative analysis highlights the advantages, limitations and intended application environment of different systems [9].

Transhumance, which involves moving bee colonies to flourishing areas to ensure high productivity, has become widespread in the beekeeping process. Transport systems are designed to reduce the risk of bee damage and ensure the safety of hives and bees throughout the process.

The main components of transport systems are:

1. Cooling mechanisms to maintain a constant temperature and humidity inside the hives, preventing heat shock to the bees and damage to food reserves,
2. Fixing devices to ensure a stable position of the hives during movement, including clamps, brackets and supports,
3. Shock-absorbing elements to maintain the internal structure of the hives, preventing damage to cellular structures and the filling and loss of honey.

The efficiency of the transport system is directly related to the uninterrupted work of the beekeeper, the health of the bees and the maintenance of product quality.

Various structural and technological solutions are used to store hives, ensuring the safety of not only bees, but also honey and technical equipment [10].

The main means of storage structures are:

1. Raised platforms - basic protection of hives from moisture, cold soil and predators, as well as the possibility of easy cleaning and movement.
2. Standardized storage cells - for convenient arrangement of hives and providing a separate space, which reduces the likelihood of damage caused by transport or technical interventions.
3. Protective covers - protection from external climatic factors - rain, wind, direct sunlight, as well as protection of bees and materials during long-term storage of hives.
4. Storage systems should be designed taking into account local climatic conditions, bee breed, number of hives and storage periods. A properly designed storage structure significantly reduces the duration of work, the likelihood of damage and increases the efficiency of beekeeping.

The main physical parameters monitored in hives are:

1. Temperature – maintaining a constant temperature inside the hive (range 34–36 °C) is important for the development of the hive, the quality of honey and the vital activity of the bees.
2. Humidity – the relative humidity inside the hive is measured to prevent the formation of mold and to ensure that the moisture content of the honey and peripheral cells is not damaged.
3. CO₂ level – an indicator of the efficiency of ventilation of units and rooms, high CO₂ levels can affect the health of bees and the activity of the hive.
4. Ventilation volume – ensures a stable microclimate inside the hive, prevents the formation of condensation points and a decrease in oxygen levels.

The purpose of measuring physical parameters is to prevent disturbances in vital activity, as well as to improve the health and productivity of the hive.

In recent years, the use of digital monitoring has been rapidly developing in beekeeping, allowing immediate and accurate monitoring of the condition of hives and prediction of development trends. Modern digital systems include:

1. Bluetooth and Wi-Fi sensors for measuring temperature, humidity, CO₂ levels and movement,
2. Electronic scales for measuring changes in hive weight, which allow estimating the volume of honey, royal jelly and food reserves,
3. Automatic data logging programs - software such as BeeWatch, Broodminder, which automatically collect and analyze physical and biological data.

These digital solutions allow predicting:

1. Nest development - for timely intervention,
2. Feed stock depletion - for optimizing food replenishment,
3. Risks of diseases and aggressive behavior - for early warning and preventive measures.

Modern control and digital monitoring systems significantly increase the efficiency of beekeeping, reduce human intervention and ensure high-quality products, preserving the natural behavior of bees and the health of the hive [5].

Supplementary device systems are especially important in intensive and industrial beekeeping, where high efficiency, disease prevention and preservation of the natural behavior of the hive are required [11].

Feeding systems.

In weak spring periods, as well as during periods of lack of floral resources, supplementary feeding of bees is a vital necessity, since natural floral reserves may not be enough to meet the needs of the hive. Supplementary feeding contributes to the health of the hive, increasing the activity of bees and maintaining productivity, as well as preventing the mortality of young bees due to lack of food.

The main types of feeding systems are:

1. Stem feeders (Fig. 22) are designed for the distribution of liquid food, such as sugar solution or honey mixtures. These feeders provide equal access to all bees in the hive, reduce clutter, and allow for precise control of consumption.

Fig.22 Stem feeders

Fig.23 Top-type containers

Fig.24 Syrup dividers

2. Top-type containers (Fig. 23) are placed at the top of the hive, ensuring continuous access to food without interfering with the natural activity of the hive. This system reduces the frequency of intervention, ensures the preservation of the natural behavior of the bees and improves feeding efficiency.

3. Syrup dividers (Fig. 24) allow you to divide the food into small groups, control the rate of consumption, reduce food loss and prevent aggressive behavior between bees. The dividers are designed taking into account the size of the hive and the spatial behavior of the bees, ensuring optimal food distribution.

The important requirements for the design of feeding systems are:

1. Food safety of the materials,
2. Easy cleaning and disinfection,
3. Physical durability for long-term use,
4. Minimal need for intervention to maintain the natural behavior of the hive.

The effectiveness of feeding systems largely depends on their correct installation, frequency of use and accuracy of dosage [6].

In intensive beekeeping practice, treatment and prevention devices ensure early detection of diseases, maintenance of hive health and effectiveness of intervention. They are important for increasing hive productivity, reducing the frequency of intervention and maintaining the natural behavior of bees.

The main devices are:

1. Disinfection devices (Fig. 25) are used to ensure the microbial safety of hives, feeding containers and equipment. Disinfection methods include liquid solutions, steam or cream applications, preventing the occurrence of epidemic situations.

Fig.25 Disinfection devices

Fig.26 Precision dosing devices

Fig.27 Vaporizers

2. Precision dosing devices (Fig. 26) allow bees to receive drugs or treatment solutions in precise doses, reducing the risk of using too much or too little medicine. This increases the effectiveness of treatment and reduces the frequency of interventions.

3. Vaporizers (Fig. 27) are used against parasites (e.g., mealybug, red spot), allowing for non-invasive poisoning of cells and bees. The vaporizer method preserves the natural behavior of the hive, reduces the need for intervention, and increases the effectiveness of treatment.

The effectiveness of treatment and prevention devices depends on their correct use, accuracy of dosing, and timely intervention.

Conclusion.

The development of beekeeping technologies demonstrates a continuous interaction between biological knowledge, engineering solutions, and practical agricultural experience.

The hive remains the central spatial, ecological, and functional unit of the bee colony. Its structure must provide stable thermoregulation, proper humidity balance, effective ventilation, safe food storage, and the preservation of natural movement pathways within the colony. The study shows that scientifically grounded hive design, based on the biological and behavioral characteristics of bees, plays a crucial role in maintaining colony health and ensuring efficient honey production.

Different structural hive systems—vertical modular, horizontal, and combined designs—offer various advantages depending on the scale of production, environmental conditions, and management practices. The selection of construction materials, such as wood, composite materials, and insulating foams, significantly influences the thermal stability, durability, and maintenance requirements of hive structures.

Modern beekeeping also relies on a wide range of technological tools and devices designed to support colony management, honey extraction, supplementary feeding, disease prevention, and safe working conditions for beekeepers. Ergonomically designed tools reduce physical strain during long working periods, while protective clothing systems ensure safety during interaction with bee colonies.

The integration of digital monitoring technologies represents an important step in the modernization of beekeeping practices. Sensors, electronic scales, and automated data analysis systems allow beekeepers to continuously monitor key physical parameters such as temperature, humidity, and hive weight, enabling early detection of potential problems and more efficient management of colonies.

Overall, the successful development of modern beekeeping depends on the harmonious

combination of biological principles, engineering design, technological innovation, and environmental sustainability. The application of scientifically based technological solutions not only increases productivity and product quality but also contributes to the preservation of bee health and the stability of ecosystems in which pollinators play a vital role.

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